

Difficulties Encountered by Kindergarten Teachers in the Modular Instruction

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.14556314

Frecelda R. Velonta

Teacher, Department of Education, Philippines

<https://orcid.org/0009-0004-6842-1327>

Abstract

The study aimed to determine the difficulties encountered by kindergarten teachers in modular instruction in two of the Districts in Negros Oriental Division as basis for an intervention plan for the school year 2021-2022. There were thirty-five (35) respondents using the descriptive research design using the researcher-made survey questionnaire. In the analysis of the results of the study, the researcher used descriptive and comparative procedures. The statistical tools used frequency, percentage, mean, and the Mann-Whitney U test. Findings showed that the degree of difficulties encountered by kindergarten teachers in modular instruction in the area of compliance with the weekly home learning plan was "high degree." The degree of difficulties encountered by kindergarten teachers in modular instruction in the area of individual learning monitoring plans was "high degree." In addition, the degree of difficulties encountered by kindergarten teachers in modular instruction in the area of performance-based assessment was "high degree." Meanwhile, when the respondents are grouped according to age, civil status, highest educational attainment, and average family monthly income, the degree of difficulties encountered by kindergarten teachers in modular instruction in the areas of compliance with weekly home learning plan, individual learning monitoring plan, and performance-based assessment was "high degree." Further, there is no significant difference existed in the degree of difficulties encountered by kindergarten teachers in modular learning modality in the areas of compliance of weekly home learning plan, individual learning monitoring plan, and performance-based assessment when they are grouped and compared according to the aforementioned variables.

Keywords: Difficulties encountered, kindergarten teachers, modular instruction

Introduction:

Nature of the Problem

The Philippines is facing a big challenge in the educational system nowadays. Due to the threat of the Covid-19 pandemic, traditional face-to-face learning is not suitable to implement and the Department of Education presented its Basic Education Continuity plan, to get the education of the country's learners back on its road. For this, different learning modalities are being proposed and one of them is Modular Instruction which is widely used by most schools nowadays. But during the implementation process of the said learning modality, different challenges have been encountered among teachers, learners, and parents (Mañalac, 2021).

Modular instruction is one of those teaching approaches where the learners have to learn everything in the module using their effort at their own pace. This method differs from the traditional one wherein a teacher presents the lesson and the learners just listen to learn the concepts presented. It is unrestricted self-learning package in which instantaneous reinforcement, a comment is provided to practice exercise, which stimulates the students and builds curiosity in them (Ambayon, 2020).

At the onset of the implementation of modular instruction, the researcher personally experienced the various difficulties encountered by kindergarten teachers. Most kindergarten teachers faced difficulties in preparing a weekly home learning plan that suits the current situation which is prescribed in the DepEd Order No. 42, s. 2016. Developing individual learning activities is another issue that causes too much pressure on kindergarten teachers since there are limited learning resources available. Moreover, conducting and formulating performance-based assessments was also problematic to them since they have limited interaction with the learners and parents. To gain success in modular instruction, difficulties, problems, and significant issues should be revealed. Revealing these problems is important for reducing or solving the barriers in modular instruction implementations to be conducted in the future.

As a kindergarten teacher, the researcher was motivated to conduct this study to determine the difficulties encountered by kindergarten teachers in modular instruction to propose an intervention plan to help kindergarten teachers minimize the difficulties faced by the kindergarten teachers and grow professionally with ease and comfort.

Current State of Knowledge

Teachers, as the spearhead of the implementation of modular instruction, must be able to condition all instructional components. These include instructional methods, media that will be used in learning, use of instructional time related to the time of application use, and psychological and social factors that significantly affect teachers' motivation when teaching. Teachers have tasks and responsibilities that are not easily transferrable when they must change from the face-to-face learning system in the classroom to an online system coupled with online learning experiences that have never been implemented before. A teacher must overcome all the problems that occur in online learning responsively so that the learning continues to achieve the targets set (Rasmitadila, et al (2020).

Meantime, according to Apriyanti (2020) kindergarten and primary school teachers face problems during the Covid-19 pandemic such as parents were unable to guide their children to learn and children's lack of concentration, unwillingness to learn, desire to go to school, inability to learn online and limited comprehension of the material. Fauzi et al. (2020) also identified that teachers face problems in the Covid-19 pandemic such as lack of opportunities, network and internet use, planning, implementation and evaluation of learning, and collaboration with parents. Mailizar et al. (2020) showed that teacher, school, curriculum and student were the four components of problems experienced by teachers in the Covid-19 period. Moreover, Rasmitadila et al. (2020) found that teachers face problems in distance education implemented in the Covid-19 pandemic such as technical barriers, student's conditioning, student's participation in education and online education experience.

Assessment of learning in a modular instruction place a challenge for teachers in determining the actual learning of the learner considering that they study at home and thus the teacher cannot see the actual situation compared to face to face setting. Performance-based assessment is a critical aspect of the teaching and learning process. It enables teachers to address the current issues in educational assessment and to measure the effectiveness of teaching with student performance to specific learning objectives. It is important to assess the performance because it provides feedback on what extent students are successfully meeting the course objectives. There are many assessment tools developed to assess the knowledge of the student learned in the classroom (Anu, 2022).

Teachers face various challenges and difficulties under the current normal education system. These challenges and problems include teaching the learners where it is difficult for teachers to reach out to all the learners at home, even the teachers are using different forms of communication. It is therefore quite difficult for them to develop the skills of the learners because the learners remain at home while learning the lessons. Not all parents have the desire and ability to support their children in their studies. Some parents lack the ability to comprehend the handwritten details written on the modules. DepEd constantly implements multiple systems that have culminated in the loss of the teachers. In this phase of the pandemic, it is difficult to gather everybody to carry out the various DepEd services. Difficulties are part of a life that cannot be erased. Individuals need to consider these obstacles in order to realize that they are living spines. In addition, they need to have a positive temperament in their lives so that they can cope with the difficulties they face in carrying out their everyday tasks at school (Canonizado, 2021).

Theoretical Underpinnings

The present investigation was anchored on Situational Problem Theory (Kim and Grunig, 2011). The situational problem theory attempts to explain why and how an individual communicates during difficulties and problematic situation. This theory has an assumption that "the more one commits to difficulty/problem resolution, the more one becomes acquisitive of information pertaining to the difficulty and problem, selective in dealing with information, and transmissive in giving it to others. When an individual tries to solve a problem and difficulties, his or her communicative activeness increases in three domains of communication action: information acquisition, selection, and transmission (Kim and Grunig, 2011).

As link in the present study, the focus was to determine the difficulties encountered by kindergarten teachers and how they are able to handle it to successfully implement the modular instruction, especially in the preparation of weekly home learning plan, individual learning plan, in the conduct of performance-based assessment. By understanding the difficulties and recognizing problems he/she therefore can find a solution. So that the kindergarten teacher remains responsible for carrying out their duties, achieving learning objectives and goals. Kindergarten teachers facilitates the transfer of learning from the experiential activity to the real world, structure the process of reflection in order to derive the most learning from the experience, and ensure that the learning outcomes are reached.

Objectives

The study aimed to determine the difficulties encountered by kindergarten teachers in the modular instruction in two of the Districts in a large-sized schools Division, in central Philippines for the school year 2021-2022 as basis for an intervention plan. Specifically, this sought to answer the following questions: 1) the degree of difficulties encountered by kindergarten teachers in the modular instruction according to Compliance of Weekly Home Learning Plan, Individual Learning Monitoring Plan, and Performance-Based Assessment; and 2) the significant difference in the

degree of challenges encountered by kindergarten teachers in the modular instruction when grouped and compared according to aforementioned variables.

Methodology

This section presents the discussion of the research methodology used, the subjects and respondents of the study, the research instruments used, the validity and reliability of the instruments, the procedure for data gathering, and the statistical tools and procedure for data analysis.

Research Design

Descriptive research design was used to determine the degree of difficulties encountered by kindergarten teachers in the modular instruction in two of the Districts in Negros Oriental Division as basis for an intervention plan for the school year 2021-2022. This method provides a way to describe the nature of a situation as it exists at the time of the study. According to De Belen (2015), descriptive design is appropriate for studies which aim to find out what prevail in the present conditions, held opinions and beliefs, processes and effects and developing trends. It is also used to determine the degree or direction of attitude, behaviors and challenges felt by the participants. Descriptive research design was appropriate to be used, since the present study also aimed to find out the prevalent conditions, gather information about the difficulties encountered by kindergarten teachers in the modular instruction.

Study Respondents

The respondents of the study were the 35 kindergarten teachers in two of the districts in Negros Oriental. The researcher purposely selected the kindergarten teachers as respondents. Purposive sampling is a form of non-probability sampling in which researchers relies on their own judgment when choosing members of population to participate in the study. Researchers use purposive sampling when they want to access a particular subset of people, as all participants of a survey are selected because they fit a particular profile (Ames et al., 2019). Table 1 shows the data.

Instruments

The study utilized the researcher-made questionnaire. Part 1 focused on the Personal Information includes the age, civil status, highest educational attainment and average family monthly income of the respondents and Part 2 will be the degree of difficulties encountered by kindergarten teachers in the modular instruction. The instrument was divided into three areas and each area is composed of ten (10) line questions. Each part of the questionnaire required the participants to read the items and simply mark the preferred option, except for the first part related to their personal information. The degree of difficulties encountered by kindergarten teachers in the modular instruction in each item was measured using 5-point likert scale with 5 as always, 4 as often, 3 as sometimes, 2 as rarely and 1 as almost never. The average rating of the three jurors was used as basis for the validity of the instrument. Validation average is 4.59, interpreted as "excellent". This showed that the research instrument was "Valid". And the reliability result was 0.780 which signifies that said instrument is highly reliable.

Data Gathering Procedure

The researcher asked permission through written communication from the Schools Division Superintendent of the Division of Negros Oriental, district supervisors, and from respective school heads of the public elementary schools, requesting to allow the researcher to distribute the questionnaires to the target respondents. After granting the permission, the researcher distributed the survey questionnaire to each respondent. The purpose of the study was properly explained to respondents by the researcher. The researcher gave the respondents an allowance of four weeks to ensure that all items in the questionnaires are answered. The questionnaires personally retrieved by the researcher after the allowed time was through to ensure a 100 percent retrieval of the checklist and questionnaires.

Data Analysis and Statistical Treatment

Objective No. 1, used descriptive-analytical scheme and mean to determine the degree of difficulties encountered by kindergarten teachers in the modular instruction.

Objective No. 2, used comparative analytical scheme and Mann- Whitney U test to determine whether there is a significant difference in the degree of difficulties encountered by kindergarten teachers in the modular instruction when they are grouped and compared according to profile variables.

Ethical Consideration

This research paper strived to minimize the risk of harm to its target respondents by assuring them of the confidentiality of their responses and protecting their anonymity throughout and beyond the research process. At the onset, this researcher secured their free, prior informed consent and assured them of their right to withdraw from their research participation if deemed necessary. The research did not harm nor endanger the chosen respondents by following the protocols of getting their prior informed consent, ensuring voluntary participation, anonymity, and confidentiality of their responses.

Results and Discussion

This section deals with the presentation, analysis and interpretation of data gathered to carry out the objectives of this study. All these were made possible by following certain appropriate procedures so as to give the exact data and solution to each specific problem.

Table 1
Degree of Difficulties Encountered by Kindergarten Teachers in the Modular Instruction in the Area of Compliance of Weekly Home Learning Plan

Items	Mean	Interpretation
<i>As a Kindergarten Teacher, I encountered difficulties in...</i>		
1. developing weekly home learning plan that are aligned in the Most Essential Learning Competencies (MELCs).	4.20	High Degree
2. preparing weekly home plan with a long-term vision of what the kindergarten learners need to master and achieve competencies at the end of the school year.	4.09	High Degree
3. collaborating with colleagues to come up with a set of weekly home learning plan for the entire quarter/grading period by integrating all domains in one learning plan.	4.23	High Degree
4. accomplishing the weekly learning plan by taking into consideration the learning domains needed to track kindergarten learner's progress.	4.11	High Degree
5. developing weekly home learning plan that respect the unique context and diversity of kindergarten learners in terms of their readiness, learning interest, and learning profile.	4.00	High Degree
6. preparing weekly home learning plan that the domains prescribed to be taken by learners is appropriate to kindergarten stage.	4.17	High Degree
7. tracking or monitoring the learners for what they learn in the day-to-day general learning process as prescribed in the weekly home learning plan.	4.23	High Degree
8. preparing weekly home learning plan that strike a balance between academic rigor and socio-emotional aspect of the kindergarten learners.	4.34	High Degree
9. communicating with the parents orient the content, purpose and use of weekly home learning plan for reference and guidance.	4.23	High Degree
10. preparing weekly home learning plan which is prescribed in the DepEd Order No. 42, s. 2016.	3.97	High Degree
Overall Mean	4.16	High Degree

As presented in table 1, the respondents assessed an overall mean score of 4.16 interpreted as "high degree." It only shows that most of the kindergarten teachers experienced much difficulties with regards to compliance of weekly home learning plan. However, if we go deeper in the analysis, the respondents assessed a highest mean score of 4.34 on item No. 8 which states "preparing weekly home learning plan that strike a balance between academic rigor and socio-emotional aspect of the kindergarten learners" interpreted as "high degree." On the other hand, the lowest mean of 3.97 was on item No. 10 which states "preparing weekly home learning plan which is prescribed in the DepEd Order No. 42, s. 2016" interpreted as "high degree."

The results imply that mostly of the kindergarten teachers are having difficulties to comply with the weekly home learning plan wherein the learning activities must strike a balance between academic and socio-emotional aspect of the kindergarten learners. Added to that, kindergarten teachers also find difficult to communicate with the parents to discuss with them the purpose of weekly home learning plan. Thus, monitoring and tracking learners' progress is very difficult for them. The current teaching-learning set-up and the no physical interaction between teacher and learners are some of the reasons that most kindergarten teachers find it difficult to formulate learning plans. The total development of a learner is not only an academic aspect but also a socio-emotional aspect as well. Socio-emotional learning is the process by which each learner develops skills that allow them to recognize, express and manage emotions, build healthy relationships, establish positive goals and respond adequately to personal and social needs.

According to Department Memorandum Order No. 162 of 2020, in preparing weekly home learning plan, there are various unique and critical parts that needs to consider which serves as a guide for instruction and contains details of what a teacher and learners will do in order to meet the required learning competencies.

Table 2
Degree of Difficulties Encountered by Kindergarten Teachers in the Modular Instruction in the Area of Individual Learning Monitoring Plan

Items	Mean	Interpretation
<i>As a Kindergarten Teacher, I encountered difficulties in...</i>		
1. preparing learning plan to develop the socio-emotional skills of kindergarten learners through activities such as autonomy, working with other, self-regulation, and how to relate with other people, schools, and community.	4.29	High Degree
2. crafting learning plans to help kindergarten learners understand and demonstrate knowledge and thinking skills in Mathematics through the use of concrete objects or materials, and to apply these meaningfully in their daily experiences.	4.31	High Degree
3. developing kindergarten learners' communicative skills by conducting activities such as using greeting, polite expressions, following instruction, expressing ideas and recalling information or stories.	4.17	High Degree
4. preparing learning plans to improve learners numeracy skills through activities such as recognizing and writing numerals, comparing quantities, etc.	4.20	High Degree
5. preparing activities to help kindergarten learners develop their language, literacy, and communication skills through reading, writing, and communicating using their first language.	4.43	High Degree
6. preparing individual learning plan to help develop kindergarten learners' aesthetic sense and creative expression through activities such as drawing, painting, and manipulative activities.	4.17	High Degree
7. crafting learning plans for the values development of kindergarten learners through activities such as respecting teachers and elders, concern for self and others, behaving appropriately in places, manifesting love of God, country, and fellowmen.	4.31	High Degree
8. creating individual learning plan to help kindergarten learners develop their physical health and motor skills through activities such as good healthy habits and fine motors skill such as balancing, scribbling, drawing, building with blocks, etc.	4.46	High Degree
9. developing activities to help kindergarten learners acquire the essential skills and sustain their natural curiosity in their immediate environment through exploration, discovery, observation, and relate their everyday experiences using their senses (touch, sight, smell, taste, and hearing).	4.43	High Degree
10. preparing learning plans to improve the cognitive skills of the kindergarten learners through activities such as identifying attribute of objects match, sort, arrange objects in sequence reasoning and problem-solving skills.	4.23	High Degree
Overall Mean	4.30	High Degree

The results in table 2 disclosed wherein the respondents assessed an overall mean score was 4.30 and interpreted as "high degree." This shows that most kindergarten teachers experienced a great challenge preparing and developing individual learning monitoring plan for kindergarten learners. If we investigate the results further, the respondents perceived a highest mean score of 4.46 on item No. 8 which states "creating individual learning plan to help kindergarten learners develop their physical health and motor skills through activities such as good healthy habits and fine motors skill such as balancing, scribbling, drawing, building with blocks, etc." and interpreted as "high degree," while the lowest mean of 4.17 was on item No. 3 which states "developing kindergarten learners' communicative skills by conducting activities such as using greeting, polite expressions, following instruction, expressing ideas and recalling information or stories" and item No. 6 which states "preparing individual learning plan to help develop kindergarten learners' aesthetic sense and creative expression through activities such as drawing, painting, and manipulative activities" interpreted as "high degree."

This implies that most kindergarten teachers are struggling to create individual learning plans that would help develop kindergarten learners' physical and motor skills. Kindergarten learners need actual interaction with the teachers, peers and in the environment in order to develop their physical and motor skills as well as their communication skills. However, because of the current educational set-up kindergarten teachers find difficult to create and implement learning activities to develop the physical and motor skills of the kindergarten learners which is very important in their total development. In addition, most kindergarten teachers are facing 'myriad of issues' when it comes to learning preparations. Also, teachers are being challenged by the scarce resources and materials to be used and unresponsive kindergarten parents. According to Department Memorandum Order No. 162 of 2020, Individual Learning Monitoring Plan is a more specific tool which shall be used by teachers and learning facilitators for learners who lag behind. Individual Learning Monitoring Plan serves as the document that will show if the learners has shown either mastery of the learning competencies, significant progress, or insignificant progress.

Table 3
Degree of Difficulties Encountered by Kindergarten Teachers in the Modular Instruction in the Area of Performance-Based Assessment

Items	Mean	Interpretation
<i>As a Kindergarten Teacher, I encountered difficulties in...</i>		
1. preparing performance-based assessment that help develop higher and critical thinking of the kindergarten learners.	4.09	High Degree
2. developing performance-based assessment to measure the socio-emotional skills of the kindergarten learners.	4.17	High Degree
3. developing a performance-based assessment that involves solving realistic problems, oral or psychomotor skills.	4.26	High Degree
4. conducting assessment activities to measure kindergarten learners' language literacy and communication skills.	4.20	High Degree
5. formulating assessment tools with learning outputs such as learners' written works, drawings and products.	4.26	High Degree
6. conducting a wide range of multi-sensorial assessment activities that determine learners' progression.	4.34	High Degree
7. developing explicit performance criteria which measure the extent to which learners have mastered the knowledge and skills.	4.23	High Degree
8. conducting assessment to give the learners the freedom to express and interact in diverse ways.	4.03	High Degree
9. conducting assessment through group performance tasks.	4.31	High Degree
10. giving feedbacks on the learners' performance-based results such as the strengths, weaknesses etc. after the presentation or outputs.	4.31	High Degree
Overall Mean	4.22	High Degree

The results in table 3 revealed results wherein the respondents assessed an overall mean score was 4.22 and interpreted as "high degree." From the result, it is clear that most kindergarten teachers encountered great difficulties in conducting performance-based assessment. However, if we examine further the items in table 5, respondents assessed a highest mean score of 4.34 on item No. 6 which states "conducting a wide range of multi-sensorial assessment activities that determine learners' progression" interpreted as "high degree." Whereas, the lowest mean of 4.03 was on item No. 8 which states "conducting assessment to give the learners the freedom to express and interact in diverse ways" interpreted as "high degree."

This implies that most kindergarten teachers encountered difficulties in the conduct of multi-sensorial assessment activities to determine learners' progress. This is because there is no actual physical interaction with the kindergarten learners, and the teacher finds it difficult to conduct multi-sensorial assessment activities. Kindergarten teachers do not really know whether the learners performed the tasks and activities since parents serves as their para-teacher. Multi-sensorial assessments such as learning through sounds, hearing and listening, seeing and watching, using our sense of touch, etc. need to have actual face-to-face interaction with the teacher and learners. According to Masaoay and Litao (2021), Performance-based assessment is a process used to track the progress of learners' in terms of learning standards and skills development in the 21st century. When implemented properly, assessment tools and strategies can have a positive impact on key aspects of the reform of education that allows a broader range of skills to be assessed instead of mere content recall. Performance-based assessment are tasks that require students to employ the knowledge and skills they have acquired by creating a product or delivering a performance.

Table 4
Difference in The Degree of Difficulties Encountered by Kindergarten Teachers in the Modular Instruction in the Area of Compliance of Weekly Home Learning Plan When Grouped and Compared According to the Aforementioned Variables

Variable	Category	N	Mean Rank	Mann Whitney U	p-value	Sig. level	Interpretation
Age	Younger	16	17.72	147.50	0.881		Not Significant
	Older	19	18.24				
Civil Status	Single	10	15.80	103.00	0.418	0.05	Not Significant
	Married	25	18.88				
Highest Educational Attainment	Lower	13	17.42	135.50	0.796		Not Significant
	Higher	22	18.34				

Average Family Monthly Income	Lower	14	14.93	104.00	0.144	Not Significant
	Higher	21	20.05			

As reflected in table 4, for variable age, the computed U is 147.50 with a p -value of 0.881 which is greater than 0.05 level of significance, thus, interpreted as "not significant." Therefore, the hypothesis that states "there is no significant difference in the degree of difficulties encountered by kindergarten teachers in modular instruction in the area compliance of weekly home plan when they are grouped and compared according to age" is accepted. Moreover, in terms of variable civil status, the computed U is 103.00 with a p -value of 0.418 which is greater than 0.05 level of significance, thus, interpreted as "not significant." Therefore, the hypothesis that states "there is no significant difference in the degree of difficulties encountered by kindergarten teachers in modular instruction in the area compliance of weekly home plan when they are grouped and compared according to civil status" is accepted.

On variable highest educational attainment, the computed U is 135.50 with a p -value of 0.796 which is greater than 0.05 level of significance, thus, interpreted as "not significant." Therefore, the hypothesis that states "there is no significant difference in the degree of difficulties encountered by kindergarten teachers in modular instruction in the area compliance of weekly home plan when they are grouped and compared according to highest educational attainment" is accepted. Further for variable length of service, the computed U is 104.00 with a p -value of 0.114 which is greater than 0.05 level of significance, thus, interpreted as "not significant." Therefore, the hypothesis that states "there is no significant difference in the degree of difficulties encountered by kindergarten teachers in modular instruction in the area compliance of weekly home plan when they are grouped and compared according to average family monthly income" is accepted. This implies that the degree of difficulties by kindergarten teachers in modular instruction in the area of compliance with the weekly home plan when they are grouped and compared according to age, civil status highest educational attainment, and average family monthly income do not vary. This is because most of the kindergarten teachers had experienced the same problem onset of the implementation of modular instruction regardless of their age, civil status, educational attainment, and average family monthly income.

Table 5
Difference in The Degree of Difficulties Encountered by Kindergarten Teachers in the Modular Instruction in the Area of Individual Learning Monitoring Plan When Grouped and Compared According to the Aforementioned Variables

Variable	Category	N	Mean Rank	Mann Whitney U	p-value	Sig. level	Interpretation
Age	Younger	16	19.25	132.00	0.500	0.05	Not Significant
	Older	19	16.95				
Civil Status	Single	10	17.20	117.00	0.766	0.05	Not Significant
	Married	25	18.32				
Highest Educational Attainment	Lower	13	20.32	112.00	0.281	0.05	Not Significant
	Higher	22	16.59				
Average Family Monthly Income	Lower	14	15.96	118.50	0.328	0.05	Not Significant
	Higher	21	19.36				

As depicted in table 5, for variable age, the computed U is 132.00 with a p -value of 0.500 which is greater than 0.05 level of significance, thus, interpreted as "not significant." Therefore, the hypothesis that states "there is no significant difference in the degree of difficulties encountered by kindergarten teachers in modular instruction in the area individual weekly home learning plan when they are grouped and compared according to age" is accepted. Moreover, in terms of variable civil status, the computed U is 117.00 with a p -value of 0.766 which is greater than 0.05 level of significance, thus, interpreted as "not significant." Therefore, the hypothesis that states "there is no significant difference in the degree of difficulties encountered by kindergarten teachers in modular instruction in the area individual weekly home learning plan when they are grouped and compared according to civil status" is accepted.

On variable highest educational attainment, the computed U is 112.00 with a p -value of 0.281 which is greater than 0.05 level of significance, thus, interpreted as "not significant." Therefore, the hypothesis that states "there is no significant difference in the degree of difficulties encountered by kindergarten teachers in modular instruction in the area individual weekly home learning plan when they are grouped and compared according to highest educational attainment" is accepted. Further for variable length of service, the computed U is 118.50 with a p -value of 0.328 which is greater than 0.05 level of significance, thus, interpreted as "not significant." Therefore, the hypothesis that

states “there is no significant difference in the degree of difficulties encountered by kindergarten teachers in modular instruction in the area individual weekly home learning plan when they are grouped and compared according to average family monthly income” is accepted.

This implies that the degree of difficulties encountered by kindergarten teachers on modular instruction in the area of individual learning monitoring plans when they are grouped and compared according to age, civil status, highest educational attainment, and average family monthly income does not differ. This only shows that majority of the kindergarten teachers are experiencing the same problems in the preparation of individual learning monitoring plans. Kindergarten teachers’ profile variables are not an influencing factor that differs their attitude in the preparation of individual learning monitoring plans.

Table 6
Difference in the Degree of Difficulties Encountered by Kindergarten Teachers in the Modular Instruction in the Area of Performance-Based Assessment When Grouped and Compared According to the Aforementioned Variables

Variable	Category	N	Mean Rank	Mann Whitney U	p-value	Sig. level	Interpretation
Age	Younger	16	20.81	107.00	0.133		Not Significant
	Older	19	15.63				
Civil Status	Single	10	17.95	124.50	0.985	0.05	Not Significant
	Married	25	18.02				
Highest Educational Attainment	Lower	13	20.73	107.50	0.222		Not Significant
	Higher	22	16.39				
Average Family Monthly Income	Lower	14	19.36	128.00	0.519		Not Significant
	Higher	21	17.10				

As presented in table 6, for variable age, the computed U is 107.00 with a *p*-value of 0.113 which is greater than 0.05 level of significance, thus, interpreted as “not significant.” Therefore, the hypothesis that states “there is no significant difference in the degree of difficulties encountered by kindergarten teachers in modular instruction in the area performance-based assessment when they are grouped and compared according to age” is accepted. With regards to the variable civil status, the computed U is 124.50 with a *p*-value of 0.985 which is greater than 0.05 level of significance, thus, interpreted as “not significant.” Therefore, the hypothesis that states “there is no significant difference in the degree of difficulties encountered by kindergarten teachers in modular instruction in the area performance-based assessment when they are grouped and compared according to civil status” is accepted.

On variable highest educational attainment, the computed U is 107.50 with a *p*-value of 0.222 which is greater than 0.05 level of significance, thus, interpreted as “not significant.” Therefore, the hypothesis that states “there is no significant difference in the degree of difficulties encountered by kindergarten teachers in modular instruction in the area performance-based assessment when they are grouped and compared according to highest educational attainment” is accepted. Further for variable length of service, the computed U is 128.00 with a *p*-value of 0.519 which is greater than 0.05 level of significance, thus, interpreted as “not significant.” Therefore, the hypothesis that states “there is no significant difference in the degree of difficulties encountered by kindergarten teachers in modular instruction in the area performance-based assessment when they are grouped and compared according to average family monthly income” is accepted. This implies that the degree of difficulties encountered by kindergarten teachers on modular instruction in the area of performance-based assessment when they are grouped and compared according to age, civil status highest educational attainment, and average family monthly income does not vary. Most kindergarten teachers are experiencing the same degree of difficulties in conducting the performance-based assessment. Regardless of their age, civil status, educational attainment, and the average family monthly income they encountered the same difficulties in conducting assessment activities for kindergarten learners.

Conclusions

On the bases of the foregoing findings of the study, the researcher arrived at the following conclusions:

Most of the kindergarten teachers struggles in the preparation of learning activities that balance academic and socio-emotional aspect of the kindergarten learners.

Majority of them encountered problem in the creation of individual learning activities that can develop learners' physical and motor skills.

In addition, many of the kindergarten teachers faced a great challenge in conducting group performance tasks assessment.

Further, the degree of difficulties encountered by kindergarten teachers in modular instruction did not vary regardless of their age, civil status, highest educational attainment, and average family monthly income.

Recommendations

Based on the findings and conclusions the following recommendations were advanced:

In the area of compliance with the weekly home learning plan, it is therefore recommended, that the School Heads should set up a School-Based Learning Action Cell (LAC) that will engage in a collaborative learning session to solve the shared difficulties in the preparation of the weekly home learning plan. Likewise, SGOD chief must initiate a division-wide training and workshop for all kindergarten teachers in crafting a weekly home learning plan that follows the learning domain of kindergarten development. In addition, Kindergarten teachers must conduct an orientation for kindergarten parents on their roles and responsibilities in the weekly home learning plan.

In the area of the individual learning monitoring plan, it is therefore recommended that the CID Chief should initiate special training for all kindergarten teachers in developing an individual learning plan. Likewise, initiate innovations and creativity in the preparation of individual learning plan that adheres to the seven learning domains in kindergarten such as physical, motor, and socio-emotional skills of the learners. Kindergarten teachers are encouraged to attend Webinars and online training on lesson planning for the kindergarten program.

In the area of performance-based assessment, it is recommended that the Public Schools District Supervisors should initiate training for all kindergarten teachers in the preparation of the performance-based assessment. Special training must be done on crafting assessment activities that focused on the multi-sensorial abilities of the learners. The Kindergarten Education Program Specialist should also formulate a ready-made performance-based assessment to be used by teachers for the kindergarten program. Further, Kindergarten teachers must conduct a regular homeroom PTA meeting to discuss with the parents the progress and development of the learners.

Acknowledgment

This endeavor will not become successful without the concerted effort and support of the researcher's adviser who always extended her untiring guidance and assistance in the making of this research, panel members during the final oral defense, for the abilities and skills being shared for the realization of this work and to her husband, who serves as her strength and for extending his moral and financial support. And lastly, a sincere appreciation and gratitude to those who, in one way or another, have contributed to the realization of this work.

References

- Alvarez, M. (2021). Issues and concerns of teachers in Mindanao State University-Sulu towards modular distance learning approach: An analysis. *Indonesian Community Empowerment Journal*, 1(2), 40-41. <https://doi.org/10.37275/icejournal.v1i2.12>
- Ambayon, E. (2020). Modular-based approach and student's achievement in literature. *International Journal of Education and Literary Studies*, 8(3). <https://doi.org/10.7575/aiac.ijels.v.8n.3p.32>
- Apriyanti, C. (2020). Distance learning and obstacles during Covid-19 outbreak. *Jurnal Ilmiah Pendidikan Dasar*, 7(2), 68-83.
- Anu, V. (2022). Assessment Challenges for Teachers in School Education. <https://www.embibe.com/exams/assessment-challenges-for-teachers-in-school-education/>
- Aviles, G., Maloloy-on, M., Olano, AJ., Arnibal, J., Arnado, A. (2021). Teachers' Critical Challenges and Opportunities in Modular Distance. *International Journal for Innovation Education and Research*. ISSN 2411-2933
- Bluman, Allan G. (2015). *Elementary Statistics: A Step by step Approach*. 9th edition. Published by McGraw-Hill Education. Penn Plaza, New York, USA.
- Canonizado, Isagani C. (2021). Modular Approach in Teaching and Learning: The Experiences of Parents and Learners. HubPages. <https://discover.hubpages.com/education/>
- Castroverde, F. (2021). Modular distance learning modality: Challenges of teachers in teaching amid the Covid-19 pandemic. *International Journal of Research Studies in Education*, 10(8), 7-15. <https://doi.org/10.5861/ijrse.2021.602>
- Dahl, Gordon & Lochner, Lance. (2015). The Impact of Family Income on Child Achievement: Evidence from the Earned Income Tax Credit. *American Economic Review*. 102. 1927-1956. [10.1257/aer.102.5.1927](https://doi.org/10.1257/aer.102.5.1927).

- Dangle, Y. R. P., & Sumaoang, J. D. (2020). The implementation of modular distance learning in the Philippine secondary public schools. In 3rd International Conference on Advanced Research in Teaching and Education, 100, 108. <https://www.doi.org/10.33422/3rd.icate.2020.11.132>
DepEd Memo Order No. 047, series of 2016.
- DepEd Memo Order No. 162, series of 2020.
- Donita-Schmidt, Smadar (2020). Opportunities and Challenges: Teachers Education in Israel in the Covid-19 Pandemic. *Journal of Education for Teaching*. Volume 46, Issue No. 4 <https://doi.org/10.1080/02607476.2020.1799708>
- Farlex, K. (2018). Changing Profile of Teachers in the Digital Age. *Journal of Educational Education*.
- Fauzi, I., & Khusuma, I. H. S. (2020). Teachers' elementary school in online learning of Covid-19 pandemic conditions. *Jurnal Iqra': Kajian Ilmu Pendidikan*, 5(1), 58-70.
- Jayani, Padzmahal G. (2021). Teachers' Perception on Modular Distance Learning Approach at Mindanao State University: Its Readiness and Challenges Open Access Indonesia Journal of Social Science.
- Karacabey, Mehmet F. (2017). The Problems that Pre-School Teachers' Encounter. *European Journal of Education Studies*. ISSN 2501-1111 Vol. 3, Issue No. 10 <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.1011868>
- Lacy, Samantha and Guirguis, Ruth. (2017). Challenges for New Teachers and Ways of Coping with Them. *Journal of Education and Learning*. 6. 265. [10.5539/jel.v6n3p265](https://doi.org/10.5539/jel.v6n3p265).
- Masaoay, Sheila Marie B. and Litao, Rodrigo A. (2021). Belief and Practices in the Implementation of Tasks: Basis for the Development of Enhancement Program. *Middle Eastern Journal of Research in Education and Social Sciences (MEJRESS)* ISSN 2709-0140 Vol. 2, Issue No. 3. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.47631/mejress.v2i3.291>
- Mayasari, Linda and Kemal, Isthifa (2020). The Role of Teachers in Implementing Distance Learning in the Middle of the Covid-19 Plague. *Systematic Review in Pharmacy*. Volume 11, Issue No. 12.
- Mañalac, Melody C. (2021). The Challenges of Modular Distance Learning. DepEd Bataan Publication
- Meador, Derrick (2019). Problems for Teachers that Limit Their Overall Effectiveness. ThoughtCo. <https://www.thoughtco.com/problems-for-teachers-that-limit-their-overall-effectiveness-3194679>
- Mishra, P., Pandey, C. M., Singh, U., Keshri, A., & Sabaretnam, M. (2019). Selection of appropriate statistical methods for data analysis. *Annals of cardiac anaesthesia*, 22(3), 297-301. https://doi.org/10.4103/aca.ACA_248_18
- Naparan, G. and Castaneda, IL (2021). Challenges and Coping Strategies of Multi-Grade Teachers. *International Journal of Theory and Application in Elementary and Secondary School Education*. Volume 3 Number 1. ISSN 2684-7167 <https://journals.researchsynergypress.com/index.php/ijtaese>
- Nardo, Ma. Theresa. B. (2017, October 20). Modular Instruction Enhances Learner Autonomy: *American Journal of Educational Research*. 2017, 5(10), 1024-1034
- Ntumi, Simon (2016). Challenges Pre-School Teachers Face in the Implementation of the Early Childhood Curriculum in the Cape Coast Metropolis. *Journal of Education and Practice*. ISSN 2222-1735 Vol 7 No. 1
- Phan, T. T. N., & Dang, L. T. T. (2017). Teacher Readiness for Online Teaching: A Critical Review. *International Journal Open Distance E-Learn*. IJODEL, 3(1), 1-16. Philippine Statistics Authority 2017
- Rasmitadila, Aliyyah, R. R., Rachmادتullah, R., Samsudin, A., Syaodih, E., Nurtanto, M., & Tambunan, A. R. S. (2020). The Perceptions of primary school teachers of online learning during the COVID-19 Pandemic period: A case study in Indonesia. *Journal of Ethnic and Cultural Studies*, 7(2), 90-109. <http://dx.doi.org/10.29333/ejecs/388>
- Sari, T., Nayir, F. (2020). Challenges in Distance Education During the (Covid-19) Pandemic Period. *Qualitative Research in Education*, 9(3), 328-360. doi:10.17583/qre.2020.5872
- Shuttleworth, Martyn (2015). How to write a research paper: An introduction to academic writing. First Edition.
- Talimodao, AJ and Madrigal, D. (2021). Printed Modular Distance Learning in the Philippine Public Elementary Schools in Time of COVID-19 Pandemic: Quality, Implementation, and Challenges. *Philippines Science Journal*
- Umar, Abdul Majeed (2018). The Impact of Assessment for Learning on Students' Achievement in English for Specific Purpose. *English Language Teaching*. Vol. 11, No. 2 ISSN 1916-4742.
- Zain, A., Basir, J. M., & Rafi, M. F. A. M. (2021). Challenges Faced by Preschool Teachers in Implementing Physical Activity During Home-Based Teaching and Learning. *International Journal of Academic Research in Business and Social Sciences*, 11(11), 910 – 919.